

“Documentation and Preservation of Textiles” – A Special Reference to Kalamkari Art of Sri Kalahasti in Andhra Pradesh”

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ABSTRACT: “With a long tradition of handicrafts, there’s arguably nowhere else on earth that produces as prolific an array of handicrafts as India. India has a rich legacy of ancient art techniques, including hand-woven and painted textiles, metal ware, wood carving, stone carving, floor coverings, toys and dolls, embroidery, jewelry and pottery. Each region has evolved with its own styles influenced by the local environment and life patterns. Andhra Pradesh is one of those regions which has inherited a wealth of traditional arts and crafts, many of which have come to find favour with art lovers not only in India but in many parts of the world. The uses of Kalamkari fabrics are varied. They can be used for decorative or functional purposes. Kalamkari was practiced mainly in Machilipatnam, Palakollu and Srikalahasti in Andhra Pradesh. The word Kalamkari literally means ‘working with a pen’. The instrument is made of a bamboo stick. There were two types of kalams, one is a pen like sharp pointed kalam and other is a brush like instrument. Srikalahasti is one the main pilgrimage Saivite center located near the banks of the Swarnamukhi river in the Tirupati district of Andhra Pradesh. This religious destination also popular as a main source for Kalamkari textile art which depict hand painted stories and themes of Ramayana and Mahabharata. An attempt is made in this paper to discuss about a systematic field survey on the Origin, Tools and Methods, Making Process, Theme depicted on the fabric and temple art of Kalamkari in detail. Select pictures are included where ever necessary.”

KEYWORDS: Handicrafts, Kalamkari, Srikalahasti, Themes, Traditional art and Crafts.

Fig:1 Kalamkari Art

Past History:

The production of textiles for export in India was concentrated mainly on the Coromandel coast, in Gujarat and in Bengal while the northern Coromandel, the area between the rivers Krishna and Godavari are specialized in the production of plain textiles. The weavers were not concentrated in northern Coromandel coast in towns but rather dispersed in industrial villages scattered throughout the south coastal Coromandel area. (Om Prakash, 1998) Painting being one of the most basic expressions of visual art and design, which is a medium that has achieved heights in terms of explorations in different techniques. Indian artists established different insights of tradition and culture by creating accord visually on a wide array of surfaces like metal, terracotta, glass, trees and almost all possible mediums. Textiles are considered as the most widely used canvas for Indian artists.

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Andhra Pradesh is one of those regions which has inherited a wealth of traditional arts and crafts, many of which have come to find favour with art lovers not only in India but in many parts of the world. Srikalahasti is one of the main pilgrimage Saivite centre located in the Tirupati district of Andhra Pradesh, 39 kms from Tirupati an ancient Vaishnavite pilgrimage city. Srikalahasti has one of the ancient Shiva temples in southern India, located on the banks of Swarnamukhi river which acts as a main source for popular textile painting called Kalamkari which depict hand painted stories and themes of Ramayana and Mahabharata. The word Kalamkari literally means ‘working with a pen’ made of a bamboo stick. There were two types of kalams, one is a pen like sharp pointed kalam and other is a brush like instrument. (Satyanarayana, K) Kalamkari paintings are flexible and washable, and the technique of fixing the dyes been perfected to such an extent that tapestries dating back to the 17th and 18th centuries still retain their jewel like colors. Kalamkari paintings had a social change that transformed this purely religious textile art form into a vibrant textile printing tradition that dazzled the entire world with the beauty of its designs and colors.

Origin:

The Origin of Kalamkari is traced to the mists of antiquity. The finding of a resist-dyed piece of cloth on a silver vase in the ancient site of Harappa confirms that the tradition of the mordant process, of which kalamkari is a typical example, is very old. The word ‘Kalamkari’ is derived from Urdu word (Qalam) and Persian ‘Kalam’ which means pen and ‘Kari’, which means artistic work. It is an art of decorating hand-loom fabric with natural dyes by a twig given the shape of a pen.

It is believed that the painted or printed fabrics were prevalent during the Indus Valley Civilization, before the advent of the Christ. Even though the ‘Chlintzes’ and ‘Calicos’ of East Coast subsequently trade named ‘Kalamkari’, were subjects of a flourishing trade as far back as the first century CE; they are said to have been in vogue even earlier as could be seen from the fact that the Buddhist chaityas and viharas were decorated with kalamkari cloth and even the Greeks under Alexander were said to have acquired this cloth. The archaeological evidences tell us that the hand painted/printed with resists-dyed cloth was discovered in the 8th century CE. The popularity of this art was found in the old writings of the French traveler, Francois Bernier.

This art flourished during the Mughal period and in 16th and 17th centuries, the items made by them were kanal or tent covers used during encampments, prayer mats etc. The hub of this art form was Golconda region, Chennai and Machilipatnam. Since Golconda was under the Muslim rule, the artistic designs produced in Machilipatnam catered to Persian tastes while Srikalahasti was under Hindu rulers, it flourished directly under the patronage of temples, and figures were drawn exclusively to narrate mythological stories. The items made with Kalamkari fabric, such as bed covers, linen and clothing for men and women, were exported to Europe and Iran since 15th or 16th century. Kalamkari was known to the European merchants i.e., Portuguese as pintado, the Dutch silz, and the British chintz. In the 19th century the pen was replaced by block-printing.

It is practiced by artists belonging to various communities mainly from two districts of Andhra Pradesh namely; Srikalahasti of Tirupati district and Machilipatnam of Krishna district. Kalamkari in Srikalahasti has been around for 300 years approximately. Unlike other places where this particular craft is practiced, artists in Srikalahasti retain the ancient techniques of dyeing which have been passed down from generations. Kalamkari probably started in south India to illustrate temple rituals. The main artist families involved in Kalamkari during the 19th century were members of the Balija community traditionally involved in agricultural work and small industry. Today, there are over 300 individuals in and around Sri Kalahasti involved in some aspects of Kalamkari work, from preparing cloth and dyes, to design motifs and format layout, to final painting and execution.

Tools and Methods of Technique:

A distinctive feature of Kalamkari is the use of vegetable colors by the artist. Unlike other paintings, which use emulsifiers and binders, Kalamkari paintings on cloth are produced by the application of dyes extracted from natural sources like roots, leaves, flowers and fruits. In Srikalahasti, the cloth is directly painted on with the pen made from bamboo sticks with felt wrapped to it. The pen which is used in the outlines are sharp compared to the one used to fill in large areas. Burnt tamarind sticks are also used to draw the outlines, kalamkari maggam, a wooden frame is used while painting, which secures the cloth on both ends. In Machilipatnam, the intricate lines of pen are transferred onto wooden blocks and finally get printed on the cloth surface. The cloth is produced in a manner where the block makers, washer people and printers work under the same roof.

In Srikalahasti, it is still the family that engages in the entire process, the solution for line drawings is locally called as kasim, which is made by adding sugarcane jaggery, palm jaggery and rusted iron into water. The solution is kept for around 21 days before using. The pen made of trimmed bamboo stick and wrapped with a piece of cotton cloth tied with thread thoroughly is dipped into kasim, squeezed and used for drawing over the cloth surface. For yellow, dust of ripe myrobalan fruit, mixed with alum solution is used, for blue, indigo is used and red was derived from the chay root found in the sandy soils.

Different colours of vegetable dyes used are:

1. Mayrabolan (Karakha Pindhi mixed with cow or Buffalo milk) forms light yellow.
2. Kassim kaaram (Jaggery, Rusted iron filings, water mixed) black outlines for the fabric.
3. Natural Indigo produces Blue.
4. Pomegranate produces Golden yellow.

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5. Catechu (Suryadu chakka) produces Rosemary.
6. Algerian produces Red.
7. Alum mixed with water gives out Gray.
8. Cow Milk (Highlights the colour on the fabric)

Fig:2 Pictures showing the natural colours used in the kalamkari work are extracted from Algerian, Indian, Pomegranate peels and burnt tamarind tree sticks.

Natural vegetable dyes were discovered by our ancestors through a lot of effort and persistence, natural dyes can be found in various different places. There are around 500 colour giving plants, but only a few are found in abundance which are cost effective and produce good colour which can be used in textile industries. Mayrabolan is actually a fruit which can be obtained from Terminalia chebula, this basically forms a pale yellow/greenish yellow colour. It also acts as a natural mordant and is used in textiles. This particular fruit is used because of the high tannin content in it. Mayrabolan is available in powdered form which costs around 200 rupees per kg. This treatment also helps the fabric to absorb required metallic mordant.

- Kasim kaaram (Black colour) is obtained from jaggery, rusted iron filings and water. Initially these materials are immersed in water and allowed to settle for around 15 to 20 days. The reaction of molasses and iron filings is called ferrous acetate. This solution when drawn on Mayrobalan seeds treated cloth turns into a permanent black because of the reaction between ferrous acetate and tannin, it is later stored in a drum or a closed container.
- Indigo blue is said to be one of the most ancient natural dyes which is obtained from Indigo leaves which is mixed with locally available sand, near river banks and allowed to settle and then filtered. The filtered solution is mixed with indigo leaves and left for around 21 days, if the process is done in less or more amount of time the output of indigo blue is either dull or too dark. So, 21 days is the appropriate time for the right shade of Indigo blue.
- The upper part of the fruit pomegranate also called persistent calyx which is finely powdered and mixed with water, stirred and then boiled to high temperatures where it becomes a fine paste and then stored. After a week's time, this paste is squashed by hand and yellow colour is produced. It is also available in the market for 800 rupees per kg.
- Algerian is a chemical which is readily available in the market for 2000 rupees per kg, in olden days the seeds of pomegranate, alum and bark of mango tree were mixed to make red colour. Kalamkari artists usually prefer buying it from the local market because it is expensive and not easily available.
- The colour green is obtained by mixing two colors; yellow and blue resulting in darker shade of green, Yellow and black forms a lighter shade of green. There are various other colors, which are used at times on customer's requests or orders, some of the colors are pigment based.

Drawing the Design:

Small tamarind sticks are burnt and covered with sand, in order to cool them gradually without making them brittle. If water is added to the fire the sticks become useless for drawing outlines on fabric. Burnt tamarind sticks act as a pencil when drawn on the fabric. Artisans make themselves comfortable on the floor while drawing outlines using a scholar's writing desk, they stretch the fabric and clip it on both ends which makes it easier for the artisans to draw. Only experienced artisans are preferred to draw the outlines as it has to be elegant and precise, it takes usually three months for a trainee to learn to draw the outlines and fifteen days to learn color filling in the fabric. Running designs are drawn free hand without any reference for experienced artisans. However experienced artisans directly draw outlines with black colour (kassim karam) using kalmkari pen. Under extreme temperatures kassim cannot be drawn on the fabric as it spreads, so in the month of April and March Kalamkari work happens during early hours in the morning.

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Tracing is usually done on special customer orders or on a particular theme which artisans are not familiar with the design, master draws the outline/design on the butter sheet or tracing paper and small holes are pierced along the borders on the sheet. The tracing sheet is then kept on the fabric and black powder is sprinkled along the borders.

Wooden frame also known as kalamkari maggam which is adjustable on two sides. Once the fabric is attached at one end it is then stretched slightly to the other end secured and locked using a wooden piece locally called karaa. The wooden frame can be adjusted even at the later stages if the artisan requires more elasticity in the fabric. Usually, thin cloth goes on to the frame because it easier to draw and paint, much thicker fabric like cotton is laid on the ground with a woolen cloth underneath for protection.

Fig:3 Skilled masters draw the designs with hand as shown in this picture and the novice artists follow the tracing method shown in the adjacent picture.

Making Process:

Kalamkari being one of the earliest and most complex techniques of textile painting uses natural vegetable dyes for colours, different sarees can take up to 2 to 3 months for completion and a simple one may complete in 10 days also, however many artists involve themselves in a single saree while painting. The outline is drawn by the experienced craftsmen and the areas inside are drawn by the less experienced. Making of Kalamkari can be classified into 3 different steps. Kalamkari can be done on any material unlike olden days where only cotton was used. Silk, Tussar, Chiffon, Georgette are some of the different materials on which kalamkari printing can be done. Kalamkari painting involves a whole of 23 to 25 steps of dyeing, bleaching, hand painting, outlining, drawing, washing and ironing, in short, chanderi or cotton cloth is bought from the market and washed in plain water to remove starch and dried, then washed and soaked in a solution of cow dung, milk and chebulic mayrobalan locally called karakha pindhi for approximately 1 to 2 hours and dried, which is ready for the basic outline is done, outlines are drawn in black colour with the help of a thin bamboo stick (kalam), the inside are then hand painted with a single colour and again washed in plain water. For maroon/red colour the cloth is soaked in boiling water for the colour to stick to the fabric. The washing process repeats until all the colors are applied. At the final stage, the cloth is washed, ironed and packed accordingly to be sent to the customer.

Fig:4 Different methods of Kalmkari making

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Theme:

In earlier times where, folk singers used to travel from one village to another narrating stories of Ramayana, Mahabharata to the village people. The ten most famous incarnations of lord Vishnu is collectively known as Dashavatar. Different stories and scenes of Hindu mythology are revealed as art in dupattas and sarees. In Kalamkari paintings of Srikalahasti the scenes from Ramayana and Mahabharata are depicted in a row with a narrative written beneath it. Some paintings describe a single episode and some an entire epic like Sampurna Ramayana. The Hindu sacred texts vedas call Mahalakshmi; a Lakshmyidhi Lakshmi which means she is the one who has the object and aim of uplifting mankind. She is often shown sitting on a big lotus flower by Kalamkari artists. Some of the paintings depict local epics such as the Katamaraju Katha, in other words, narrative genealogy of the Gollas, and Katama Raju is the epic’s hero, the caste champion. The paintings are not just religious, moral and spiritual in character but also means to record social events. Equally prominent are the motifs based on flora and fauna, especially the ‘Tree of Life’ is a mystical concept alluding to the interconnectedness of all life on our planet and metaphor for common descent in evolutionary sense. It is used by kalamkari artists in various forms and sizes.

The cloth is used as a canopy or backdrop in temples. In Machilipatnam, the majority of fabrics are meant for clothing, prayer mats, bed spreads, tapestry and hangings. A variety of motifs used for these fabrics range from stylized plants, creepers, geometric designs to animals and human figures.

Kalamkari depicted in the Temple Art:

Kalamkari evolved as a tradition of its own of producing painted scrolls incorporating Hindu mythological themes used as temple hangings. This could have been a sequel to the demand from the well-known temple centers of South India as well as Andhra Pradesh in which we can see even today large and impressive Kalamkari cloth paintings, covering themes such as ‘Daksha Yagnam’, ‘Dasavatharam’, ‘Sitarama Kalyanam’, ‘Sampoorna Ramayanam’, ‘Dhruva vijayam’, ‘Meenakshi Kalyanam’, ‘Venkateswara Chritam’, etc. In Srikalahasti the style of drawing on the fabric is characterized by bold, black, angular lines inspired by the murals from temples such as Veerabhadraswamy temple, 16th century C.E., Lepakshi, and Sri Chennakesava temple, Sompalem, in Andhra Pradesh. Kalamkari designs, motifs and painting forms have emerged from inspirations from palaces, monuments and temples found in India, along with designs of wildlife.

Colorful painting of Lord Krishna playing the flute.

A photo framed painting of Lord Ganesha playing Dholak and dancing.

Fig: 5 Examples of Kalamkari Art (Final)

CONCLUSION:

The unique art of Kalamkari in India has variety of themes to please fashion aspirants. It was a favourite art form for both Islam and Hindu thrones. This prominent art work involves natural colors, traditional methods and most importantly, the craftsmen ship passed on from generations. Kalamkari from Sri Kalahasti reflects a predominately Hindu patronage, and artists in the area continue that tradition through the painting of a variety of Hindu narrative themes, including the Ramayana, Mahabharata, and Shiva Purana of Mythological themes. Sri Kalahasti in the 19th century flourished directly under the patronage of temples, with their demands for hanging with strong figurative and narrative components. Thus fabrics exhibiting rich vibrancy of natural colors painted to depict mythological tales have become a unique character of Kalamkari at Sri Kalahasti.

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